

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 1.4 to AD4.1 – Information Leaflet for Adolescents

WP 4

Partnership
FOR THE
Assessment
OF
Risks
FROM
Chemicals

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the European Union

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Project approved by *[specify name of the committee]* with ref. n° XXXXX

PARC_GS_Information leaflet for Adolescents

Information Leaflet for Adolescents

We are inviting you to take part in a research study called "PARC". Before you decide if you want to take part, please read this leaflet and ask us any questions you may have. We will be very happy to answer them!

Chemical pollutants

Our bodies, the food we eat, the water we drink and the products we use every day are made of chemicals, on which we depend to stay healthy, be productive and enjoy life. But sometimes food, air and products may be polluted by "hazardous" chemicals, which are able to cause damage to people and the environment. Chemical pollutants are a type of "environmental pollutant".

Why are we performing this study?

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Our team of researchers from 28 European countries is working to find the connection between the environment's quality and people's health. Our project is called "PARC" (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals) and it is funded by the European Commission and our *national government*.

Why should I care?

PARC's purpose is beneficial in several ways.

1. It works to understand how exposed we are to dangerous chemicals and if this may affect our health.
2. It aims to discover whether measures that are used across Europe are enough to protect us from chemicals that are threatening our health or if new measures must be taken.

Is the research safe and who has checked it?

The study is respecting the European and national laws for ethics and the protection of personal data and it was approved by [*XX Research Ethics Committee*]. We make sure that our studies are safe because we want to better people's lives, not endanger them.

Why are you asking me?

You are the future of our society and you can help our mission!

You are invited because we wish to study adolescents who are [*XX to YY*] years old and live in [*ZZ name of sampling region*]. [*Describe any other appropriate inclusion criteria*].

If you decide to take part, you will be one of [*specify number: ...*] teens in [*specify your country: ...*] and a total of [*specify number: ...*] teens in [*specify total number of participating countries: ...*] European countries, who will participate in our study.

What does participation in this research mean?

We will ask you to provide [*adjust as applies to the specific study: samples of urine / blood / hair*] and to answer with your parents, a questionnaire which has simple questions about your daily life (daily habits, food, location of your house..... Explain that trained personnel will do the sampling and if it will be done at home or a study center (give location) and give an estimation of how long the time commitment of the adolescence will be].

[Delete all matrices in the following which are not part of your study. Please adapt if needed. Please consider the document "Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples to be used in PARC]

Which samples and how my samples will be taken?

Urine: We ask you to provide a urine sample in the plastic container provided. The urine sample has to be the first morning void. The sample collection is done by yourself at the toilet at your home. You will receive detailed written instruction for the collection of the sample.

Blood: We ask you to provide a blood sample. The blood will be always taken at the Examination Centre **[where]** by medical staff. Maybe your blood have had be taken in your life before by a doctor, and you already know about it. The blood collection for our study is very similar. Before the blood is taken, your skin is disinfected. During the sampling, a cannula is inserted through your skin into your vein at your arm, and venous blood is then drawn into blood tubes via the cannula and a sampling tube. The sampling is taken quickly and takes only a moment. Only a few millilitres are taken **(insert number of tubes)**. After the blood sample is taken, you press the puncture site with a swap for some minutes. You receive a plaster over the puncture site. Done!

Hair: *[Insert easy-to-understand text describing the hair sampling in detail]*

What will happen to my samples and data?

Your samples and data will be used only according to your consent and in a way to protect your privacy according to the law.

NOBODY will have the right to gain access to your identifying personal information and data.

Our scientists assign a code to your samples and data and will remove any information that identifies you. Your data will be stored pseudonymized. This means that only the study owner can combine the code with your personal data. This will be done to protect your privacy.

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Your coded samples will be examined in specialized laboratories [adjust as necessary: in our country and abroad]. Small amounts of your coded samples will be stored in a 'BioBank'. This means that your coded samples will be stored under appropriate conditions, so that they may be used in future studies similar to this one. Your coded data will be kept in computerized 'DataBases'.

The Data Controller for any personal data that we will hold about you is [provide name and contact details]. If you have any questions or concerns related to data protection, you may contact our Data Protection Officer at [provide name and contact details].

How will I benefit by taking part?

- *Describe if a gift is given as an incentive: We would like to thank you for taking part and adding value to our study by offering you ...]*
- You can feel proud for helping create a healthier environment for all the teenagers in your country and across Europe!
- In doing so, you can learn how exposed you are to the investigated chemicals and how you can help to prevent being exposed. This medical briefing is specialized and is not given to you during your typical medical examination.
- [Describe any additional incentives]

Let's work together to ensure the protection of people's health and the environment in our country and all of Europe!

How will other people benefit if I take part?

The results we are going to collect from your participation in the study will be used as a representative sample that:

- *Will help us to understand the exposures that people have to harmful chemicals*
- *Will show how the levels of such chemicals affect the body*
- *Will be used to help us develop better chemical management policies in [your country] and across Europe and justify why this is important.*

How will this study influence the decisions of politicians?

PARC partners will establish a dialogue with policy makers to ensure that the research's results can be used to:

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- Support the development of policies
- Evaluate existing policies
- design measures to reduce exposure to toxic chemicals

Do I have to participate?

Participation is absolutely voluntary and you are able to withdraw anytime without consequences and without explanations, by just letting us know.

If you decide to take part, we will ask you and your parents to complete a consent form to document this decision and that you understand the study and your rights. You will receive a copy of this form and keep it for future reference.

Why do you need my written consent?

By providing us with your written consent, you confirm that you volunteer to take part in the study after having understood what is required from you. You also confirm that you acknowledge your rights. You will also confirm if we can contact you in the future to inform you about your personal results and to perform further similar studies using your biobanked samples.

What happens if I change my mind about taking part?

After you let us know, we will destroy any samples that are left in our BioBank and all the information about you from our DataBase. Samples and information already used for research will not have any information that can identify you.

What if I have concerns or complaints while I'm taking part?

Your wellbeing is our top priority. If you have concerns during the study visit, please discuss them with our researchers or contact our study leader at any time at [name and contact information]. In the unlikely event you wish to file a complaint about the study, you may contact [name, contact info], who is an independent overseer.

**LET'S CREATE A HEALTHIER
FUTURE TOGETHER!**

Who can I ask for more information?

We will be happy to help you to find out the answers you need. Talk to our researchers or you can always reach out to our study leader **[Name Surname of Research Coordinator of the Country, Tel: [xxxxxxx], Email address**

[xxxxxxx].

Thank you for reading this leaflet and for considering to join the PARC study!

Visit our website to find out more! www.eu-parc.eu

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